

Project Summary - SPSRB (145 records selected)

Status Report: 24-August-2025
 Total Specimen Count: 145

	Sequences	GenBank Accessions
Total	145	0
COI-5P	145	0

Sequenced Specimens (145)
 Specimens Not Yet Sequenced (0)

Sequenced Specimens

100 records per page Search:

Identification	BIN	Sample ID	Museum ID	Process ID	Institution Storing	Country/Ocean	GPS	Image
Glyptothorax macromaculatus		G_macromaculatus_MH156953	G_macromaculatus_MH156953	SPSRB145-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Erethistoides senkhiensis		E_senkhiensis_MN984677	E_senkhiensis_MN984677	SPSRB001-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Erethistoides senkhiensis		E_senkhiensis_MN984681	E_senkhiensis_MN984681	SPSRB002-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Erethistoides senkhiensis		E_senkhiensis_MN984680	E_senkhiensis_MN984680	SPSRB003-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Erethistoides senkhiensis		E_senkhiensis_MN984679	E_senkhiensis_MN984679	SPSRB004-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Erethistoides senkhiensis		E_senkhiensis_MN984678	E_senkhiensis_MN984678	SPSRB005-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

Identification	BIN	Sample ID	Museum ID	Process ID	Institution Storing	Country/Ocean	GPS	Image
Pterocryptis indicus	BOLD:ADS6227	P_indicus_MN991970	P_indicus_MN991970	SPSRB006-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pterocryptis indicus	BOLD:ADS6227	P_indicus_MN991971	P_indicus_MN991971	SPSRB007-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pterocryptis indicus	BOLD:ADS6227	P_indicus_MN991972	P_indicus_MN991972	SPSRB008-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pterocryptis indicus	BOLD:ADS6227	P_indicus_MN991973	P_indicus_MN991973	SPSRB009-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pterocryptis indicus	BOLD:ADS6227	P_indicus_MN991974	P_indicus_MN991974	SPSRB010-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Amblyceps apangi	BOLD:ABX1877	A_apangi_MH156940	A_apangi_MH156940	SPSRB011-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Amblyceps apangi	BOLD:ABX1877	A_apangi_MN996555	A_apangi_MN996555	SPSRB012-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Amblyceps apangi	BOLD:ABX1877	A_apangi_MN996556	A_apangi_MN996556	SPSRB013-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Amblyceps apangi	BOLD:ABX1877	A_apangi_MN996557	A_apangi_MN996557	SPSRB014-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Amblyceps apangi	BOLD:ABX1877	A_apangi_MN996558	A_apangi_MN996558	SPSRB015-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Exostoma labiatum	BOLD:ADW6031	E_labiatum_MH156943	E_labiatum_MH156943	SPSRB016-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Exostoma labiatum	BOLD:ADW6031	E_labiatum_MN996559	E_labiatum_MN996559	SPSRB017-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Exostoma labiatum	BOLD:ADW6031	E_labiatum_MN996560	E_labiatum_MN996560	SPSRB018-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Exostoma labiatum	BOLD:ADW6031	E_labiatum_MN996561	E_labiatum_MN996561	SPSRB019-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

Identification	BIN	Sample ID	Museum ID	Process ID	Institution Storing	Country/Ocean	GPS	Image
Exostoma labiatum	BOLD:ADW6031	E._labiatum_MN996562	E._labiatum_MN996562	SPSRB020-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Channa punctata	BOLD:ACG5323	C._punctata_MH156960	C._punctata_MH156960	SPSRB021-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Channa punctata	BOLD:ACG5323	C._punctata_MN996563	C._punctata_MN996563	SPSRB022-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Channa punctata	BOLD:ACG5323	C._punctata_MN996564	C._punctata_MN996564	SPSRB023-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Channa punctata	BOLD:ACG5323	C._punctata_MN996565	C._punctata_MN996565	SPSRB024-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Channa punctata	BOLD:ACG5323	C._punctata_MN996566	C._punctata_MN996566	SPSRB025-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Labeo gonius	BOLD:AEC6518	L._gonius_MH156966	L._gonius_MH156966	SPSRB026-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Labeo gonius	BOLD:AEC6518	L._gonius_MN996567	L._gonius_MN996567	SPSRB027-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Labeo gonius	BOLD:AEC6518	L._gonius_MN996568	L._gonius_MN996568	SPSRB028-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Labeo gonius	BOLD:AEC6518	L._gonius_MN996569	L._gonius_MN996569	SPSRB029-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Labeo gonius	BOLD:AEC6518	L._gonius_MN996570	L._gonius_MN996570	SPSRB030-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax waltoni	BOLD:ACC0744	S._waltonii_MG251739	S._waltonii_MG251739	SPSRB031-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax waltoni	BOLD:ACC0744	S._waltonii_MN991975	S._waltonii_MN991975	SPSRB032-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax waltoni	BOLD:ACC0744	S._waltonii_MN991976	S._waltonii_MN991976	SPSRB033-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

Identification	BIN	Sample ID	Museum ID	Process ID	Institution Storing	Country/Ocean	GPS	Image
Schizothorax waltoni	BOLD:ACC0744	S._waltonii_MN991977	S._waltonii_MN991977	SPSRB034-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax waltoni	BOLD:ACC0744	S._waltonii_MN991978	S._waltonii_MN991978	SPSRB035-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Cyprinus carpio	BOLD:AAA7175	C._carpio_MN996571	C._carpio_MN996571	SPSRB036-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Cyprinus carpio	BOLD:AAA7175	C._carpio_MN996572	C._carpio_MN996572	SPSRB037-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Cyprinus carpio	BOLD:AAA7175	C._carpio_MN996573	C._carpio_MN996573	SPSRB038-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Cyprinus carpio	BOLD:AAA7175	C._carpio_MN996574	C._carpio_MN996574	SPSRB039-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Cyprinus carpio	BOLD:AAA7175	C._carpio_MN996575	C._carpio_MN996575	SPSRB040-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax richardsonii	BOLD:AAJ6274	S._richardsonii_MN996576	S._richardsonii_MN996576	SPSRB041-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax richardsonii	BOLD:AAJ6274	S._richardsonii_MN996577	S._richardsonii_MN996577	SPSRB042-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax richardsonii	BOLD:AAJ6274	S._richardsonii_MN996578	S._richardsonii_MN996578	SPSRB043-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax richardsonii	BOLD:AAJ6274	S._richardsonii_MN996579	S._richardsonii_MN996579	SPSRB044-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax richardsonii	BOLD:AAJ6274	S._richardsonii_MN996580	S._richardsonii_MN996580	SPSRB045-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax progastus	BOLD:AAD5904	S._progastus_MN996581	S._progastus_MN996581	SPSRB046-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax progastus	BOLD:AAD5904	S._progastus_MN996582	S._progastus_MN996582	SPSRB047-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

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Schizothorax progastus	BOLD:AAD5904	S._progastus_MN996583	S._progastus_MN996583	SPSRB048-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax progastus	BOLD:AAD5904	S._progastus_MN996584	S._progastus_MN996584	SPSRB049-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schizothorax progastus	BOLD:AAD5904	S._progastus_MN996585	S._progastus_MN996585	SPSRB050-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax trilineatus	BOLD:ACH0208	G._trilineatus_MN996586	G._trilineatus_MN996586	SPSRB051-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax trilineatus	BOLD:ACH0208	G._trilineatus_MN996587	G._trilineatus_MN996587	SPSRB052-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax trilineatus	BOLD:ACH0208	G._trilineatus_MN996588	G._trilineatus_MN996588	SPSRB053-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax trilineatus	BOLD:ACH0208	G._trilineatus_MN996589	G._trilineatus_MN996589	SPSRB054-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax trilineatus	BOLD:ACH0208	G._trilineatus_MN996590	G._trilineatus_MN996590	SPSRB055-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Danio rerio	BOLD:AAE3739	D._rerio_MN996591	D._rerio_MN996591	SPSRB056-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Danio rerio	BOLD:AAE3739	D._rerio_MN996592	D._rerio_MN996592	SPSRB057-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Danio rerio	BOLD:AAE3739	D._rerio_MN996593	D._rerio_MN996593	SPSRB058-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Danio rerio	BOLD:AAE3739	D._rerio_MN996594	D._rerio_MN996594	SPSRB059-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Danio rerio	BOLD:AAE3739	D._rerio_MN996595	D._rerio_MN996595	SPSRB060-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Salmo trutta	BOLD:AAB3872	S._trutta_fario_MN996596	S._trutta_fario_MN996596	SPSRB061-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

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Salmo trutta	BOLD:AAB3872	S_trutta_fario_MN996597	S_trutta_fario_MN996597	SPSRB062-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Salmo trutta	BOLD:AAB3872	S_trutta_fario_MN996598	S_trutta_fario_MN996598	SPSRB063-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Salmo trutta	BOLD:AAB3872	S_trutta_fario_MN996599	S_trutta_fario_MN996599	SPSRB064-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Salmo trutta	BOLD:AAB3872	S_trutta_fario_MN996600	S_trutta_fario_MN996600	SPSRB065-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax telchitta	BOLD:AAY1018	G_telchitta_MN996601	G_telchitta_MN996601	SPSRB066-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax telchitta	BOLD:AAY1018	G_telchitta_MN996602	G_telchitta_MN996602	SPSRB067-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax telchitta	BOLD:AAY1018	G_telchitta_MN996603	G_telchitta_MN996603	SPSRB068-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax telchitta	BOLD:AAY1018	G_telchitta_MN996604	G_telchitta_MN996604	SPSRB069-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax telchitta	BOLD:AAY1018	G_telchitta_MN996605	G_telchitta_MN996605	SPSRB070-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Gudusia chapra	BOLD:ABA9557	G_chapra_MN996606	G_chapra_MN996606	SPSRB071-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Gudusia chapra	BOLD:ABA9557	G_chapra_MN996607	G_chapra_MN996607	SPSRB072-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Gudusia chapra	BOLD:ABA9557	G_chapra_MN996608	G_chapra_MN996608	SPSRB073-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Gudusia chapra	BOLD:ABA9557	G_chapra_MN996609	G_chapra_MN996609	SPSRB074-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Gudusia chapra	BOLD:ABA9557	G_chapra_MN996610	G_chapra_MN996610	SPSRB075-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

Identification	BIN	Sample ID	Museum ID	Process ID	Institution Storing	Country/Ocean	GPS	Image
Pseudolaguvia shawi	BOLD:AAX7090	P_shawi_MN996611	P_shawi_MN996611	SPSRB076-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pseudolaguvia shawi	BOLD:AAX7090	P_shawi_MN996612	P_shawi_MN996612	SPSRB077-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pseudolaguvia shawi	BOLD:AAX7090	P_shawi_MN996613	P_shawi_MN996613	SPSRB078-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pseudolaguvia shawi	BOLD:AAX7090	P_shawi_MN996614	P_shawi_MN996614	SPSRB079-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Pseudolaguvia shawi	BOLD:AAX7090	P_shawi_MN996615	P_shawi_MN996615	SPSRB080-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schistura tirapensis	BOLD:ADE6356	S_tirapensis_MN996616	S_tirapensis_MN996616	SPSRB081-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schistura tirapensis	BOLD:ADE6356	S_tirapensis_MN996617	S_tirapensis_MN996617	SPSRB082-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schistura tirapensis	BOLD:ADE6356	S_tirapensis_MN996618	S_tirapensis_MN996618	SPSRB083-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schistura tirapensis	BOLD:ADE6356	S_tirapensis_MN996619	S_tirapensis_MN996619	SPSRB084-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Schistura tirapensis	BOLD:ADE6356	S_tirapensis_MN996620	S_tirapensis_MN996620	SPSRB085-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Notopterus	BOLD:AEI1973	N_notopterus_MN996621	N_notopterus_MN996621	SPSRB086-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Notopterus	BOLD:AEI1973	N_notopterus_MN996622	N_notopterus_MN996622	SPSRB087-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Notopterus	BOLD:AEI1973	N_notopterus_MN996623	N_notopterus_MN996623	SPSRB088-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Notopterus	BOLD:AEI1973	N_notopterus_MN996624	N_notopterus_MN996624	SPSRB089-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

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Notopterus	BOLD:AEI1973	N._notopterus_MN996625	N._notopterus_MN996625	SPSRB090-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax gracilis	BOLD:ADL3603	G._gracilis_MN996626	G._gracilis_MN996626	SPSRB091-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax gracilis	BOLD:ADL3603	G._gracilis_MN996627	G._gracilis_MN996627	SPSRB092-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax gracilis	BOLD:ADL3603	G._gracilis_MN996628	G._gracilis_MN996628	SPSRB093-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax gracilis	BOLD:ADL3603	G._gracilis_MN996629	G._gracilis_MN996629	SPSRB094-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Glyptothorax gracilis	BOLD:ADL3603	G._gracilis_MN996630	G._gracilis_MN996630	SPSRB095-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Chanda nama	BOLD:AAZ1771	C._nama_MN996631	C._nama_MN996631	SPSRB096-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Chanda nama	BOLD:AAZ1771	C._nama_MN996632	C._nama_MN996632	SPSRB097-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Chanda nama	BOLD:AAZ1771	C._nama_MN996633	C._nama_MN996633	SPSRB098-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	
Chanda nama	BOLD:AAZ1771	C._nama_MN996634	C._nama_MN996634	SPSRB099-20	Central Agricultural University, College of Fisheries	India	Yes	

Showing 1 to 100 of 145 entries

Specimens Not Yet Sequenced

100 records per page

Search:

Identification	BIN	Sample ID	Museum ID	Process ID	Institution Storing	Country/Ocean	GPS	Images	COI-5P GenBar
No data available in table									

Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries

Previous Next

